

Figure S2: Relation between physical size and recombination rates of linkage groups.

Spearman's correlation shows a negative trend between physical size to the recombination rate of linkage groups, although not statistically significant ($R = -0.38$, $p = 0.11$). This trend was expected since longer linkage groups will have less crossover per Mb and vice versa if we assume one obligate crossover per chromosome arm. The dark line shows a linear relationship with the shaded area represents a 95% confidence interval.

